

Peroxydisulphate Oxidation of Amino Acids—Kinetics of Oxidation of Glutamic Acid

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Ag⁺ catalysed oxidation of Glutamic acid by peroxydisulphate ion in aq. medium has been found to be first order in [S₂O₈²⁻] and in the catalyst [Ag⁺] and zero order in Glutamic acid. However, the first order rate constant decreases linearly with the increase in [S₂O₈²⁻]. A mole ratio of 1:1 has been found. The reaction exhibits negative salt effect of primary exponential type as well as specific inhibitory effect of ions in the order

Allyl acetate greatly inhibits the rate. The energy parameters are $\Delta E = 9.1 \pm 0.4$ K cal mole⁻¹; $\Delta S^\ddagger = -48.64 \pm 0.10$ e.u.; $A = 4.2 \pm 0.15 \times 10^2$ sec⁻¹, $\Delta F^\ddagger = 23.84 \pm 0.50$ K cal mole⁻¹.

A radical mechanism is proposed.

THE uncatalysed as well as Ag⁺ catalysed oxidation of various reductants by peroxydisulphate ion has been studied by a number of workers and reviewed by House¹, Wilmarth & Haim². Dakin³, Bacon, Hanna & Stewart⁴, Adinarayana, Sethuram & Rao⁵ have shown that amino acids, on oxidation, produce corresponding aldehydes. However, no kinetic study of oxidation of Glutamic acid and other amino acids by S₂O₈²⁻ has been made. Hence a detailed kinetic study of oxidation of glutamic acid by S₂O₈²⁻ in aqueous medium, catalysed by Ag⁺ ion, has been carried out by us to decide the mechanism of this reaction, the results of which are presented in this paper.

Materials and Method:

Glutamic acid of B. D. H. quality, potassium peroxydisulphate and silver nitrate of B. D. H., Analar grade were used. All the standard solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The progress of reaction was followed by estimating unreacted peroxydisulphate iodometrically by the method of Szabo, Csanyi and Galiba⁶ as modified by Khulbe & Srivastava⁷.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry—One mole of Glutamic acid is found to be oxidised by one mole of peroxydisulphate ion.

Product analysis—The reaction mixture containing 0.01 M Glutamic acid, 0.05 M K₂S₂O₈ and 0.005 M AgNO₃ was kept at 45° for four hours to complete the reaction. A gas evolves with effervescence, as the reaction proceeds, which gave positive test for CO₂

while the reaction mixture gave positive test for NH₄⁺. This indicates that oxidation of glutamic acid proceeds with oxidative decarboxylation and deamination.

The product was first characterized by TLC. For reference semialdehyde of Succinic acid was prepared by the method of Bacon, Hanna & Stewart⁴. Its 2 : 4 DNP derivative was prepared by the usual method. This 2 : 4 DNP derivative and that of the oxidation product were separately dissolved in chloroform and spotted on activated silica gel G (0.6 mm) TLC plate. The plate was developed in a mixture of n-butanol : water (9 : 1) for 45 min. The rate of development was 11.9 cm/hr. The R_F values of the two compounds was found to be the same (0.92), thus confirming that the oxidation product is semialdehyde of Succinic acid. Further, it was found that I. R. spectra of 2 : 4 DNP derivative of the oxidation product was a finger print of that of the 2 : 4 DNP derivative of semialdehyde of Succinic acid.

Kinetic Results

The Ag⁺ catalysed self decomposition of peroxydisulphate, which is first order, is appreciable at experimental temperature, and was, therefore, studied simultaneously and accounted for throughout these studies.

The reaction follows first order behaviour in [S₂O₈²⁻]. However, the first order rate constant (k_r) decreases with increase in [S₂O₈²⁻] (Table 1) at constant K⁺ ion concentration and constant ionic strength (μ was maintained constant by adding K₂SO₄) and at finite concentration of S₂O₈²⁻ follows the relationship

$$-\log k_r = 2.26 + 5.4 [S_2O_8^{2-}]_0 \quad \dots (1)$$

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The decrease in rate constant with increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$ may be due to traces of impurity present even in recrystallized Analar grade sample of $K_2S_2O_8$.

The reaction is zero order in Glutamic acid and the first order rate constant is unaffected by a change in Glutamic acid concentration (Table 2).

Table 3 summarizes the data on the effect of Ag^+ ion concentration on the rate constant. The plot of k_r vs $[Ag^+]$ is linear and follows the eqn. :

$$k_r = 3.88 \times 10^{-3} + 4.06 [Ag^+] \quad \dots (2)$$

indicating that uncatalysed oxidation also occurs at

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ ON RATE CONSTANT AT CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH ($\mu=0.331$) AND CONSTANT K^+ ION CONCENTRATION.

Glutamic acid = 0.01M;	$AgNO_3 = 0.001M;$	Temp. = 33°C;	$\mu = 0.331$
$[S_2O_8^{2-}] \times 10^3 M$	10	20	30
$k_2 \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	6.05	5.20	4.35
$k_1 \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	1.16	0.90	0.63
$k_r \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	4.89	4.30	3.72

where k_1 , k_2 are the first order rate constants for Ag^+ catalysed self decomposition of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and of total reaction (oxidation reaction & self decomposition). $k_r (=k_2 - k_1)$ is the net specific rate for the oxidation of Glutamic acid.

TABLE 2—THE EFFECT OF [GLUTAMIC ACID] ON RATE CONSTANT.

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$	$AgNO_3 = 0.001M$	Temp. = 33°C	$\mu=0.331$
[Glutamic acid] $\times 10^3 M$	10	15	20
$k_2^* \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	9.15	9.31	9.22
$k_1 \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	1.40	1.40	1.40
$k_r \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	7.75	7.91	7.82

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[Ag^+]$ ON RATE CONSTANT.

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M;$	Glutamic acid = 0.01M,	Temp. = 33°C
$[AgNO_3] \times 10^3 M$	1	1.5
$k_2 \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	9.15	12.19
$k_1 \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	1.40	1.95
$k_r \times 10^3 (min^{-1})$	7.75	10.24

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M;$	Glutamic acid = 0.01M;	$AgNO_3 = 0.001M;$	Temp. = 33°C
S. No.	$[K_2SO_4] \times 10^3 M$	$k_r \times 10^3 min^{-1}$	$-\log k_r$
1.	5	6.45	-2.1904
2.	10	4.87	-2.3125
3.	15	4.23	-2.3737
4.	20	3.64	-2.4389
5.	25	3.13	-2.5045

the temperature of the experiment, the first order rate constant of which is $3.88 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Experimentally determined value of first order constant of uncatalysed oxidation is $3.80 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

The kinetic data recorded in table 4 show that the rate constant decreases with the increase in ionic strength and a plot of $\log k_r$ vs $\mu^{1/2}$ is linear, indicating thereby that the salt effect is of primary exponential type. It is pertinent to mention that Ag^+ catalysed decomposition of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, has been found experimentally to show similar effect.

The specific inhibitory effect of different ions is rather small (table 5) which is in the order :

Table 6 gives the rate constant at different temperatures and the value of energy parameters calculated therefrom. A plot of $\log k_r$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$ is linear showing

thereby that Arrhenius eqn. is followed. The reaction is characterized by a low energy of activation and rather lower frequency factor giving a large negative value of entropy of activation.

Allyl acetate has strong inhibitory effect (Table 7) suggesting thereby that the reaction follows radical chain mechanism.

Discussion

The above kinetic data clearly demonstrate that Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of Glutamic acid by peroxydisulphate ion and its Ag^+ catalysed decomposition follows similar kinetics, which is suggestive of the fact that similar mechanism is being followed in the two processes involving similar radicals. Further, since the inhibitory effect of allyl acetate is far greater in case of glutamic acid oxidation, it suggests that allyl acetate removes the radicals produced from glutamic acid also and that this radical is also involved in interaction with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ (step v). Since the uncatalysed oxidation process also occurs at an appreciable rate at the temperature of

TABLE 5—SPECIFIC INHIBITORY EFFECT OF IONS

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.01M$; Added salt	Glutamic acid = $0.01M$	KNO_3	ZnSO_4	$0.01M$	MgSO_4	$\text{AgNO}_3 = 0.001M$, K_2SO_4	Temp. = 33°C ; NaSO_4	$\mu = 0.076$ H_2SO_4
$k_2 \times 10^3$ (min^{-1})	9.15	5.16	4.92	5.13	5.30	5.29	5.57	
$k_1 \times 10^3$ (min^{-1})	1.40	1.05	1.10	1.14	1.07	1.17	1.14	
$k_r \times 10^3$ (min^{-1})	7.75	4.11	3.82	3.99	4.23	4.12	4.43	

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE.

Temp. (k°)	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	$k_2 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	$k_r \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	ΔE K cal mole^{-1}	$A \times 10^3$ sec^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger (e.u.)	ΔF^\ddagger K cal mole^{-1}
306	1.40	9.15	7.75		4.06	-48.65	23.37
311	2.03	12.56	10.53	9.5	4.35	-48.54	23.58
316	2.70	15.42	12.72	9.0	4.15	-48.67	23.84
321	3.74	20.37	16.63	8.9	4.33	-48.62	24.06
326	5.04	24.66	19.62		4.11	-48.74	24.34
	Mean value			9.1 ± 0.4	4.20×10^3 ± 0.15	-48.64 ± 0.10	23.84 ± 0.50

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF ALLYL ACETATE ON RATE CONSTANT.

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.01M$;	Glutamic acid = $0.01M$;	$\text{AgNO}_3 = 0.001M$;	Temp. = 33° ;	$\mu = 0.031$
[Allyl acetate] $\times 10^3 M$		—	5	10
$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		9.15	2.59	1.51
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		1.40	1.25	1.15
$k_r \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		7.75	1.34	0.36

experiment, hence the total oxidation reaction is a simultaneous reaction consisting of side reactions—the uncatalysed and Ag^+ catalysed oxidation processes (1st order rate constant of uncatalysed and Ag^+ catalysed oxidation is 3.80×10^{-3} and $7.75 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively), and the uncatalysed and Ag^+ catalysed decomposition of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (1st order constants of uncatalysed and Ag^+ catalysed self decomposition is 1.01×10^{-3} and $1.40 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively). Here again it is found that the uncatalysed reaction shows similar kinetic characteristics as the Ag^+ catalysed reaction, pointing to the possibility of similar radicals being involved in the two cases.

On the basis of the kinetic results and other evidences the following mechanism is proposed for the Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of glutamic acid.

The steps (i) and (ii) have been proposed by a number of workers^{9,10} for the Ag^+ catalysed redox reactions of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. E.S.R. studies¹¹ have provided the evidence for the existence of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radical in peroxydisulphate oxidation reaction. Step (ii) is followed by step (iii) and (iv) in which H abstraction from the amino acid molecule is brought about by $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ and Ag^{2+} resulting in the formation of corresponding

radical of amino acid. H abstraction has been shown to take place in the case of other organic substrates^{12,13} also. The radical $\text{COOH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\cdot\text{COO}\cdot$ (herein after designed as R \cdot) then undergoes decarboxylation and deamination in presence of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in step (v) and in presence of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ in step (vi) to give the corresponding aldehyde.

Applying steady state treatment for the radicals Ag^{2+} , $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ & R \cdot the rate expression comes^{9,10,11,13} out to be

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = Kk_2[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{Ag}^+] + [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \sqrt{\frac{Kk_2k_3k_5[\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}]}{k_6}}$$

where S stands for amino acid taken. Since k_6 is very large in comparison to K or k_2 or k_3 or k_5 , it corresponds to radical-radical process, the last term is kinetically not distinguishable. Hence the reaction is first order in $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ and in $[\text{Ag}^+]$.

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